

Nanocomposite Hydrogels with Temperature Response for Capacitive Energy Storage

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ABSTRACT: Functional hydrogels are three-dimensional polymeric networks with potential applicability in the field of wearable electronics. However, hydrogels are often used to develop devices with only one functionality. In this work, a multifunctional hydrogel consisting of poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene) (PEDOT), alginate (Alg), carbon nanoparticles (CNPs), and manganese oxide has been manufactured for devices that can simultaneously store energy (supercapacitor) and sense temperature. The Alg and PEDOT interpenetration allows for obtaining a flexible and electrically conductive hydrogel with an open and interconnected porous structure. The incorporation of CNPs improves electrical conductivity and confers synergies with manganese oxide, which provide energy storage capability. Furthermore, the resistance of the hydrogel varies linearly with the temperature, this behavior being observed consistently and without hysteresis throughout consecutive heating and cooling cycles. Thus, the PEDOT/Alg/CNP/MnO₂ hydrogel shows good capacitance (42 mF cm⁻²), capacitance retention (87%), and good temperature sensitivity (−1.05% °C⁻¹).

KEYWORDS: alginate, carbon nanoparticles, conductive hydrogel, manganese oxide poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene), supercapacitor, temperature sensor

INTRODUCTION

Among hydrogels, which are three-dimensional network structures able to imbibe large amounts of water, conducting hydrogels (CHs) deserve consideration due to their charge (ionic and/or electronic) transport properties. CHs are excellent candidates for the fabrication of flexible electronics owing to their good conductivity, adjustable mechanical properties (i.e., stretchability, compressibility, and elasticity), multiple stimuli-responsive properties, conformability, and biocompatibility.^{1,2} Within this context, CHs have emerged as promising candidates for manufacturing flexible bioelectronic devices for diagnosis (e.g., biosensors) and therapeutics (e.g., drug-delivery systems), playing vital roles in health monitoring, soft robotics, regenerative medicine, or artificial intelligence (e.g., electronic skin).^{1,3–8} More recently, CHs have been successfully used for manufacturing flexible energy storage devices (e.g., batteries and supercapacitors for energy conversion)^{8–10} and solar water evaporator equipment for seawater desalination and wastewater purification¹¹ due to other interesting advantages, such as large surface area, porous microstructure, and easy tenability.

Among the different types of existing CHs, those prepared by incorporating carbon-based materials such as carbon nanotubes (CNTs), carbon black, and graphene into insulating hydrogels have received special attention because of the outstanding properties of the resulting nanocomposite hydro-

gels.^{12,13} For example, carbon-based CHs are widely used for sensing applications and electrical double-layer electrochemical supercapacitors due to their excellent mechanical and electrical properties as well as high surface area.^{14,15} Other nanoparticle (NP)-based CHs are those containing transition metal oxide hydrogels. These nanocomposite CHs, which utilize reversible redox reactions at the electrolyte–electrode interface, are used in pseudo-supercapacitors because of their high capacitance.^{16,17} One limitation of these single functional hydrogels, and at the same time a challenge, is that they can only match a single demand at a time, limiting their applicability.

CHs prepared by mixing poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene) (PEDOT) and alginate (Alg) have received special attention because of their multi-responsive behavior.¹⁸ PEDOT is a commercially available organic conducting polymer (CP) with outstanding conductive and electrochemical responses (i.e., high conductivity and fast redox response), high processability, mechanical robustness, improved electrical conductivity, and good biocompatibility.^{19–21} On the other hand, Alg is a

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natural, biodegradable, biocompatible, biostable, and hydrophilic polysaccharide extracted from brown algae.^{18,22} Interpenetrated hydrogels obtained by combining PEDOT and Alg, hereafter named PEDOT/Alg, simultaneously exhibit the properties of the two systems, for example, conductivity, piezoelectricity, biocompatibility, self-healing properties, and both chemical and thermoelectric responsiveness.¹⁸ Because of this, PEDOT/Alg CHs have been proposed for soft (bio)-electronics as self-healable pressure sensors,²³ drug-delivery systems,^{24,25} biosensors (when loaded with gold NPs for signal amplification),²⁶ and remotely transportable electronic devices (when loaded with magnetite NPs),²⁷ among others.¹⁸

This work goes one step further by designing a new multifunctional PEDOT/Alg hydrogel that incorporates carbon nanoparticles (CNPs) and a metal oxide, manganese oxide (MnO_2), for its simultaneous use as a flexible supercapacitor and a temperature sensor. Each material plays a relevant role within the hydrogel to get this multifunctionality. While Alg confers mechanical stability as it can be easily cross-linked by bivalent cations, PEDOT and CNPs generate an electrically conductive path across the hydrogel, and MnO_2 has a high energy storage capacity (theoretical capacitance: 1370 F g^{-1}).²⁸

METHODS

The materials and characterization methods are described in the Electronic Supporting Information, and this section reports only the preparation methods.

The hydrogels—PEDOT/Alg, PEDOT/Alg/CNP, and PEDOT/Alg/CNP/ MnO_2 —were prepared by mold casting. The utilization of a mold is essential to control the shape and dimension of the hydrogels in a reproducible manner. The process can be summarized as follows. First, equal volumes of a commercial PEDOT:PSS suspension (1.3 wt %) and a sodium alginate solution (3.9 wt %) were homogeneously mixed using a speed mixer (3500 rpm, 5 min). The mixture was injected into the mold cavity and introduced into a 0.2 M CaCl_2 solution to cross-link the polymeric chains and get the hydrogel. To prepare the PEDOT/Alg/CNP hydrogel, CNPs were added to the PEDOT/Alg dispersion to get a final content of 30 wt %. Finally, the PEDOT/Alg/CNP hydrogels were modified by chemical reduction of KMnO_4 with ethanol to get PEDOT/Alg/CNP/ MnO_2 . Hydrogels were immersed in 5 mL of ethanol (EtOH), and subsequently, 3 mL of a 0.1 M KMnO_4 solution was added. Different amounts of manganese oxide were obtained at different times, ranging from 5 to 60 min. Hydrogels were thoroughly washed in deionized water.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Preparation of the Hydrogels. PEDOT/Alg/CNP/ MnO_2 hydrogels were synthesized as shown in Figure 1. First, a homogenized dispersion of PEDOT, Alg, and CNP was poured into a mold in which the ITO-coated PET sheet was previously placed. After that, the mold was immersed in a CaCl_2 solution for Alg cross-linking. In order to incorporate the MnO_2 into the formed hydrogels, gelled samples were immersed in EtOH, and KMnO_4 was added. Hydrogels were kept for different times (5, 15, 30, and 60 min) in the reaction medium to modify the MnO_2 content coming from the reduction of permanganate. Figure 1 includes photographs of as-prepared PEDOT/Alg/CNP and PEDOT/Alg/CNP/ MnO_2 hydrogels. On the other hand, PEDOT/Alg and PEDOT/Alg/CNP hydrogels were used in subsequent characterization studies for comparison purposes.

Morphological and Spectroscopic Analysis. Figure 2A compares scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of the

Figure 1. Scheme showing the preparation procedure of the PEDOT/Alg/CNP/ MnO_2 hydrogels. Photographs of the prepared hydrogel before and after the incorporation of MnO_2 are shown.

surface of PEDOT/Alg, PEDOT/Alg/CNP, and PEDOT/Alg/CNP/ MnO_2 hydrogels after lyophilization. Although all hydrogels exhibit open and interconnected porous structures, these are more evident in PEDOT/Alg than in the CNP- and CNP/ MnO_2 -containing hydrogels (inset in Figure 2A-a1). These features represent an advantage since a high surface area is expected allowing easy access and rapid motion of the electrolyte to the hydrogel surface, favoring charge-discharge processes (i.e., high energy storage capability). On the other hand, Figure 2A-a2 evidences that the CNPs detected in PEDOT/Alg/CNP are homogeneously distributed. Finally, the incorporation of MnO_2 leads to a drastic change in the surface morphology. Thus, the PEDOT/Alg/CNP/ MnO_2 hydrogel exhibits a rough surface composed of aggregated round nanostructures.

Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) mapping (Figure 2B) allowed for detecting the homogeneous distribution of PEDOT and Alg since the S and Ca signals, which are characteristic elements of PEDOT and Alg, respectively, are equally detected through the hydrogel. In addition, EDX mapping of the element carbon is detected from the CNP, PEDOT, and Alg. Such a homogeneous distribution implies that the whole hydrogel is electrically conductive. Finally, the presence of Mn was proven to be not only on the surface but also inside the hydrogel, as the cross-section EDX mapping shows. The latter result confirms the porous and interconnected structure of the hydrogels since the diffusion of EtOH and KMnO_4 inside the polymeric network had to take place.

The Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectrum of PEDOT/Alg (Figure S1) is consistent with that already reported for such a hydrogel.²³ In addition to the broad band at 3360 cm^{-1} , which is associated with the O–H stretching, the spectrum of PEDOT/Alg displays absorption bands assigned to carbonyl ($\text{C}=\text{O}$) asymmetric and symmetric stretching of Alg at 1606 and 1418 cm^{-1} , respectively, the vibrations of the fused dioxane ring from PEDOT at 1286 and 1164 cm^{-1} , the C–O–C stretching of Alg at 1023 cm^{-1} , and the stretching of the C–S bond in the thiophene ring of PEDOT at 822 cm^{-1} . Unfortunately, the spectrum of PEDOT/Alg/CNP does not show any clear evidence of the CNPs (Figure S1), while the PEDOT/Alg/CNP/ MnO_2

Figure 2. (A) SEM images of (a1) PEDOT/Alg, (a2) PEDOT/Alg/CNP, and (a3) PEDOT/Alg/CNP/MnO₂. (B) SEM image and EDX mapping of a PEDOT/Alg/CNP/MnO₂ hydrogel cross-section. (C) Raman spectra of PEDOT/Alg and PEDOT/Alg/CNP/MnO₂ hydrogels.

recorded for samples with the highest MnO₂ content (60 min in the reaction medium) evidences the disappearance of the less intense bands from PEDOT/Alg (Figure S1). This phenomenon has been attributed to the coating effect of MnO₂, which was confirmed by recording the spectra of PEDOT/Alg/CNP/MnO₂ prepared using different MnO₂ contents (5, 15, 30, and 60 min in the reaction medium; Figure S2).

Figure 2C shows the Raman spectra of PEDOT/Alg as compared with PEDOT/Alg/CNP/MnO₂. The characteristic bands of PEDOT:PSS can be observed at 1200–1500 cm⁻¹ (c1).²⁹ Detection of the rest of the components (such as Alg) becomes very difficult as most of the characteristic vibrations are overlapped by the PEDOT signal, which in turn is enhanced by a resonance effect.³⁰ Nonetheless, the presence of CNPs can be observed at 1363 and 1520 cm⁻¹, corresponding to the disorder (D-band) and the tangential mode vibration (G-band) of CNPs, respectively.²³ Moreover, the widening and shifting of the PEDOT bands have been attributed to the strong background signal observed in CNP spectra.

On the other hand, several peaks have been detected in the region where manganese oxides are expected (400–900 cm⁻¹). However, the lower intensity of the former peaks compared to PEDOT:PSS and CNP ones makes their interpretation difficult (c2). Thus, Raman spectroscopy was run onto the MnO₂ solid

obtained after reacting EtOH and KMnO₄ without the presence of the hydrogel (Figure S3). Upon closer examination of the manganese oxide region, a sharp peak at 655 cm⁻¹, attributed to the stretching mode of MnO₆ octahedra, is observed along with some weaker peaks in the 400–620 cm⁻¹ range. This peak distribution has been assigned to γ -MnO₂, in agreement with the results reported in the literature.^{14,17,31,32} Thus, Raman spectra indicate that no significant other manganese species with characteristic Raman fingerprints, like MnOOH or ϵ -MnO₂,^{33,34} are present.

Figure 3 shows the X-ray diffraction (XRD) pattern of the composite hydrogels exhibiting peaks at 2θ values of 25, 37, 55, and 65° assigned to the (120), (021), (221), and (002) planes of γ -MnO₂, as previously reported.^{14,17,35} The broad peaks at 25, 29, and 46° can be ascribed to CNPs.^{17,36} These results are in agreement with those previously shown for Raman analysis. It is also worth noting that no impurities (e.g., Ca(OH)₂) are detected in the composite hydrogels.

Further morphologic and crystallographic characterization studies using high-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM) were also performed for the PEDOT/Alg/CNP/MnO₂ multifunctional platform. Figure 4A,B details the amorphous nature of the CNP illustrated by its twisted fringes; meanwhile, as shown in Figure 4C, direct observation of the MnO₂ NPs allowed us to quantify their average size as

Figure 3. XRD pattern of PEDOT/Alg/CNP/MnO₂. The peaks associated with γ -MnO₂ are indicated. The peaks marked with a star have been ascribed to CNPs.

Figure 4. HRTEM images of the PEDOT/Alg/CNP/MnO₂ system. (A) and (B) CNP attached to the PEDOT/Alg structure. (C) Full shot of the PEDOT/Alg/CNP/MnO₂ where the γ -MnO₂ NPs can be appreciated. (D) and (E) FFT and crystallographic planes for a γ -MnO₂ NP. (F) and (G) FFT and crystallographic planes for a ram-MnO₂ NP.

3.76 ± 1.40 nm. Moreover, close inspection of the MnO₂ NPs' lattice fringes confirmed that the γ -MnO₂ phase is predominant, confirming Raman and XRD results. Thus, as can be observed in the fast Fourier transform (FFT) of Figure 4D, detection of the 2.01 Å (120) and 2.13 Å (121) crystallographic planes was attributed to the intergrowth pyrolusite (β -MnO₂) and ramsdellite (ram-MnO₂) structures, respectively, confirming the presence of γ -MnO₂. In addition, low presence sole ram-MnO₂ NP observation (lattice fringe of 2.50 Å (021) from Figure 4F) would also be in accordance with the broad peak observed for the (021) reflection in XRD studies due to the combination of γ -MnO₂ and ram-MnO₂ NPs.

The mechanical properties of the prepared hydrogels were evaluated by quantitative nanomechanical atomic force microscopy (AFM) mapping. Table 1 lists the Young modulus (E) and the reduced Young modulus (E^*), which are both related by the samples' Poisson ratio (ν ; eq 1) of PEDOT/Alg, PEDOT/Alg/CNP, and PEDOT/Alg/CNP/MnO₂, considering different permanganate reduction times ($t = 5, 15, 30,$ and 60 min). According to the literature,³⁷ the value of ν was estimated to be 0.5.

$$E^* = \frac{E}{(1 - \nu^2)} \quad (1)$$

Table 1. Young Modulus (E) and the Reduced Young Modulus (E^*) for the Studied Hydrogels As Determined by Quantitative Nanomechanical AFM Mapping^a

sample	E (MPa)	E^* (MPa)
PEDOT/Alg	0.32 ± 0.05	0.42 ± 0.07
PEDOT/Alg/CNP	0.44 ± 0.08	0.59 ± 0.11
PEDOT/Alg/CNP/MnO ₂ ($t = 5$ min)	1.06 ± 0.08	1.41 ± 0.09
PEDOT/Alg/CNP/MnO ₂ ($t = 15$ min)	0.99 ± 0.18	1.31 ± 0.24
PEDOT/Alg/CNP/MnO ₂ ($t = 30$ min)	1.17 ± 0.31	1.57 ± 0.42
PEDOT/Alg/CNP/MnO ₂ ($t = 60$ min)	1.83 ± 0.56	2.31 ± 0.65

^aMeasurements on PEDOT/Alg/CNP/MnO₂ were performed considering permanganate reduction times (t).

The E values were obtained from the force–distance curves (representative examples of the recorded curves are provided in Figure S4). Films were examined using a cantilever with a nominal spring constant, k_s , of 5 N/m, with the set point adjusted to get a sample deformation of around 50 nm. As is shown in Table 1, the E value of PEDOT/Alg, ~ 0.3 MPa, experienced a slight increment to ~ 0.4 MPa upon the incorporation of CNPs. However, the incorporation of MnO₂ into PEDOT/Alg/CNP resulted in a more drastic enlargement of E , which indeed increased with the permanganate reduction time (i.e., from ~ 1 MPa for $t = 5$ min to ~ 2 MPa for $t = 60$ min).

Applications: Supercapacitor and Temperature Sensing. Initially, cyclic voltammetry (CV) was used to qualitatively characterize the capacitance of the different hydrogels as the integral area of voltammetric curves is proportional to specific capacitance (Figure 5A). As can be seen, the presence of CNPs increases the capacitance due to the higher electrical conductivity of the hydrogels as well as the energy storage capacity of carbon nanomaterials. However, the incorporation of MnO₂ along with CNPs and PEDOT markedly enhances the capacitance of the hydrogels that have been attributed to the following two reasons: (1) the high energy storage capacity of the transition metal oxide and (2) the low electrical conductivity of MnO₂ is minimized by the presence of CNPs and PEDOT, which confer a synergistic behavior with the inorganic oxide and, therefore, improve its performance.

Cyclic voltammograms of PEDOT/Alg/CNP/MnO₂ hydrogels are characterized by being non-rectangular and symmetric, without redox peaks attributed to the presence of pseudocapacitive materials (e.g., PEDOT and MnO₂), and the good reversibility of the adsorption/desorption and Faradaic processes (Figure 5B).¹⁴ On the other hand, the cyclic voltammograms deviate from ideal voltammetric curves (perfectly horizontal) when the scan rate increases from 25 to 1000 mV s⁻¹. Since the energy storage depends on the electrolyte entry/exit into/from the hydrogel (i.e., a diffusion-controlled process) and the diffusion of ions is a limited process, the higher the scan rate is, the lower the number of ions that successfully approach and interact with the hydrogel. Good reversibility of the energy storage processes is maintained even at higher scan rates as all the curves are symmetric independent of the scan rate.³⁴ It should be mentioned that capacitive advantages provided by the incorporation of MnO₂ were independent of the voltage window. This is illustrated in Figure S5, which compares cyclic voltammograms recorded for PEDOT/Alg/CNP/MnO₂, PEDOT/Alg, and PEDOT/Alg/CNP using a potential

Figure 5. (A) Cyclic voltammograms of PEDOT/Alg, PEDOT/Alg/CNP, and PEDOT/Alg/CNP/MnO₂ ($t = 30$ min) hydrogels at 100 mV s^{-1} . (B) Cyclic voltammograms of PEDOT/Alg/CNP/MnO₂ ($t = 30$ min) hydrogels at different scan rates.

window from -0.2 V (initial/final potential) to 0.6 V (reversal potential). Also, Figure S5 includes the voltammetric response of PEDOT/Alg/MnO₂ (i.e., without CNPs) that, as expected, displays a behavior that is intermediate between those of PEDOT/Alg/CNP and PEDOT/Alg/CNP/MnO₂, proving the synergy between MnO₂ and CNPs.

The electrochemical stability of PEDOT/Alg, PEDOT/Alg/CNP, and PEDOT/Alg/CNP/MnO₂ hydrogels was studied by CV, applying 3000 consecutive redox cycles scanning reversibly a potential window comprised between 0.0 and 0.8 V at a rate of 100 mV/s . Figure 6 compares the evolution of

Figure 6. Variation of the electroactivity (with respect to the second cycle) against the number of CV cycles (eq S1).

the electroactivity with respect to the second cycle against the number of CV cycles (eq S1). The stability of PEDOT/Alg was relatively poor, with the loss of electroactivity stabilizing at around 71% after 2500 CV cycles. The incorporation of CNPs improved the electrochemical performance, with the loss of electroactivity reaching a constant value of $\sim 40\%$ after 2000 CV cycles. This improvement was attributed to the intrinsic structural stability of CNPs in comparison with neat organic polymers (i.e., PEDOT and Alg), which underwent electrically induced chemical degradation very rapidly. Moreover, such stabilization is much more pronounced for PEDOT/Alg/CNP/MnO₂ due to the intrinsic stability of MnO₂, a crystalline ceramic material. For PEDOT/Alg/CNP/MnO₂, the loss of electroactivity with respect to the second cycle, which was $\sim 20\%$ only, stabilized after 300 cycles.

To assess the effect of flexibility on the electrochemical response of PEDOT/Alg/CNP/MnO₂, cyclic voltammograms were recorded for the as-prepared hydrogel, the bent hydrogel (i.e., the hydrogel was completely folded on itself, as shown in the inset of Figure S6), and after such drastic bending. Results,

shown in Figure S6, indicate that although the electrochemical activity decreased during folding due to percolation loss of both CNPs and MnO₂ when the hydrogel is under bending forces, the electrochemical activity largely recovers when the hydrogel comes back to the original state (after bending). Consistently, the energy densities before and after the bending were very similar (1.05×10^{-4} and $1.09 \times 10^{-4} \text{ J/m}^3$, respectively), while the energy density of the bent sample was much lower ($5.34 \times 10^{-5} \text{ J/m}^3$).

The effect of CNPs and MnO₂ on the electrical resistance (R) of PEDOT/Alg was examined by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy measurements. The resistance was obtained by adjusting the recorded Nyquist plots, which are shown in Figure S7, to a simple Randles circuit. Results show that the electrical resistance of PEDOT/Alg experiences a slight reduction upon the incorporation of CNPs ($R = 15.8$ and $14.6 \text{ k}\Omega \text{ cm}^{-2}$ for PEDOT/Alg and PEDOT/Alg/CNP, respectively). Besides, the resistance of the MnO₂-containing system is lower by one order of magnitude ($R = 3.4 \text{ k}\Omega \text{ cm}^{-2}$ for PEDOT/Alg/CNP/MnO₂), which is fully consistent with its enhanced electrochemical behavior.

After that, the performance of PEDOT/Alg/CNP/MnO₂ hydrogels prepared with different MnO₂ contents was quantitatively evaluated using galvanostatic charge–discharge (GCD) assays (Figure 7A). The area of the GCD curves and, therefore, the capacitance (eq S2) rapidly increased with the permanganate reduction time until a threshold value of 30 min was reached (Figure 7B). Thus, the capacitance of PEDOT/Alg/CNP, which was $6 \pm 1 \text{ mF cm}^{-2}$ ($t = 0$ min), increased to $9 \pm 1 \text{ mF cm}^{-2}$ after the shortest time in the permanganate reduction medium ($t = 5$ min), reaching a value of $42 \pm 2 \text{ mF cm}^{-2}$ when the time in the medium increased to 30 min (Figure 7B). Although this value is higher than the values reported for many multi-component soft materials used in wearable supercapacitors, for example, PEDOT/reduced graphene oxide hydrogels (25 mF cm^{-2}),³⁸ polyaniline/carbon nanotubes (PANI/CNT) yarn (38 mF cm^{-2}),³⁹ and graphene textile (2.7 mF cm^{-2}),⁴⁰ some single-component electroactive materials have exhibited greater values, for example, air-stable PANI ink (96 mF cm^{-2}).⁴¹ Beyond 30 min, the capacitance decreased to $19 \pm 3 \text{ mF cm}^{-2}$ (Figure 7B) due to the higher content of MnO₂ and, therefore, the lower electrical conductivity of the hydrogel. On the other hand, the GCD curves systematically deviate from the ideal triangular curves (Figure 7C) due to the pseudocapacitive materials, in agreement with the results found by CV. Despite the slight asymmetry in the GCD curves, the Coulombic efficiency (η ; eq

Figure 7. (A) GCD curves of PEDOT/Alg/CNP/MnO₂ prepared using different permanganate reduction times. (B) Variation of the specific capacitance of PEDOT/Alg/CNP/MnO₂ against the permanganate reduction time. (C) Consecutive GCD curves of PEDOT/Alg/CNP/MnO₂ prepared using a permanganate reduction time of 30 min. (D) Life cycle stability for 3000 GCD cycles.

2), which corresponds to the ratio between the charge (t_c) and discharge times (t_d), is very good ($87 \pm 3\%$).

$$\eta = \frac{t_c}{t_d} \quad (2)$$

On the other hand, no voltage drop is observed in the GCD curves, indicating that the internal resistance of the hydrogels is low due to the continuous electrical path created by CNPs and PEDOT. Finally, the life cycle was evaluated by performing 3000 consecutive GCD cycles. Around 80% of the initial capacitance was retained after such a huge number of cycles (Figure 7), indicating a good rate capability of the hydrogels.

The electrochemical performance of two PEDOT/Alg/CNP/MnO₂ supercapacitors connected in parallel and series modes was also examined. In both cases, an Alg hydrogel was used as a semi-solid dielectric medium. The recorded voltammograms are shown in Figure 8A, while Figure 8B sketches the connections between the different components for the two studied modes (photographs are displayed in Figure S8). While a vanishing effect is observed when the supercapacitors were connected in series, the current density and, therefore, the voltammetric area increased significantly for the parallel mode. This confirms the good behavior of PEDOT/Alg/CNP/MnO₂ as supercapacitors.

PEDOT/Alg/CNP/MnO₂ hydrogels were studied to be simultaneously used as temperature sensors. The normalized resistance ($\Delta R/R_0$) was measured when the temperature was increased from 20 to 60 °C considering the two orthogonal directions (Figure 9A,B). As can be observed, the sensing capacity of the hydrogel is independent of the measurement direction. The electrical conductivity of the hydrogel increases

with the temperature, leading to a decrease in the normalized resistance. This is because PEDOT and carbon nanomaterials are semiconducting materials and, therefore, their conductivity increases as the temperature rises due to the higher number of charge carriers.^{42,43} Indeed, the linear decrease of the normalized resistance is fully consistent with the semiconducting behavior exhibited by materials with a positive temperature coefficient, such as PEDOT:PSS.⁴⁴ Thus, the charge transport regime in PEDOT/Alg/CNP/MnO₂ hydrogels is thermally activated. After cooling, the same $\Delta R/R_0$ values were practically obtained while no hysteresis was detected, indicating good reproducibility of the sensor. This feature has been attributed to the fact that no water removal occurs in the temperature interval comprised between 25 and 60 °C, which could alter the chemical composition of the system and/or the mechanical consistency of the hydrogel. On the other hand, the sensitivity of the hydrogel was evaluated through the temperature coefficient of resistance (TCR) calculated as follows (eq 3):

$$\text{TCR} = \frac{R - R_0}{R_0} \times \frac{1}{\Delta T} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

The sensitivity is $-1.05 \pm 0.10\% \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$, which is significantly higher than the values reported for other materials based on PEDOT and carbon nanomaterials.^{42,43,45,46} For example, inkjet-printed samples based on carbon and PEDOT:PSS and screen-printed samples based on PEDOT:PSS/CNTs reached a TCR of 0.25 and 0.61% $^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$, respectively.^{44,45} Also other CPs, such as PANI nanofibers, have been used to fabricate temperature sensors. For example, the TCR reported for PANI electrochemically polymerized on a polyethylene terephthalate

Figure 8. (A) Voltammograms recorded for two PEDOT/Alg/CNP/MnO₂ supercapacitors connected in series and parallel (Alg hydrogel was used as a semi-solid dielectric medium). (B) Diagram showing the connections between the different components for the supercapacitors connected in series and parallel modes.

sheet was $0.61\% \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$.⁴⁶ It is important to highlight that the presence of MnO₂ does not hinder the variation of resistance with temperature. Finally, the hydrogel was reproducible as similar values were obtained after a few heating/cooling cycles (Figure 9C).

Figure 9. For PEDOT/Alg/CNP/MnO₂ prepared using a permanganate reduction time of 30 min: (A, B) variation of the normalized resistance with temperature during heating and cooling in the two directions of the sample and (C) normalized resistance after different heating/cooling cycles.

Therefore, a new strategy to develop multifunctional composite hydrogels for energy storage and temperature sensing has been designed. This is based on (i) using hydrogels with open and interconnected porosity to improve electrolyte access; (ii) incorporating CNPs and PEDOT to confer electrical conductivity for temperature sensing and create effective electron pathways; and (iii) adding MnO₂ to improve the energy storage capacity of the hydrogel.

CONCLUSIONS

In summary, multifunctional PEDOT/Alg/CNP/MnO₂ hydrogels for supercapacitors and temperature sensors have been successfully fabricated. For this purpose, initially, PEDOT/Alg/CNP hydrogels were prepared by mold casting. Next, a chemical reduction process of permanganate to MnO₂ was applied to obtain PEDOT/Alg/CNP/MnO₂. The specific capacitance increased due to the presence of CNPs as well as the incorporation of MnO₂, which is a highly capacitive material. The composite hydrogel shows good capacitance values (42 mF/cm^2) and good long-term cyclability (87%) probably due to both (1) the presence of MnO₂ into the electrically conductive CNP and PEDOT matrix and (2) the open and interconnected structure of the hydrogels that facilitates the adsorption/desorption or Faradaic processes. Finally, the PEDOT/Alg/CNP/MnO₂ hydrogels can be successfully used to sense temperature by measuring changes in the normalized resistance, showing an excellent coefficient of temperature ($-1.05\% \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$). Overall, PEDOT/Alg/CNP/MnO₂ hydrogels are promising for applications in multifunctional flexible and wearable electronics.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge at <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acsaem.3c00721>.

Materials and characterization methods, FTIR and Raman spectra, representative force–distance curves determined by quantitative nanomechanical AFM mapping, cyclic voltammograms, Nyquist plots, and photographs of two supercapacitors connected in parallel and series modes (PDF)

Complete contact information is available at: <https://pubs.acs.org/10.1021/acsaem.3c00721>

Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

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